

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

System design report

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Executive summary

The scope of this report is to describe the design of a distributed sensor network system which integrates sensors based on Arduino and low cost technologies with Open Standards Web services based on geospatial software. The report introduces the factors that may influence the design and present the requirements and the choices done with respective the motivations. The document presents the design subdividing the system in three main layers: the *hardware* to perform observations, the *services* to handle the information and the *communication* to connect sensors to servers.

1 Introduction

Board (1990) stated in his book on the importance of monitoring system that «the economic, social, and political costs of failing to detect and deal with environmental problems in the early stages can be enormous. Economically, correcting problems after the environment is seriously degraded adds to the costs. But some degradation may be irreparable: living resources may be so depleted and habitats so damaged that stocks of commercially and recreationally important species may never return to pre-degradation levels. Public health problems can arise, with attendant economic and social consequences. Public opposition and anger may increase with sudden news that beaches are unsafe for swimming or fish and shellfish are unsafe to eat. Government agencies and their officials may be blamed for neglect or short-sightedness». In these sentences there's the essence of why do we need to establish environmental monitoring systems.

According to Artiola et al. (2004) and Wiersma (2004) “environmental monitoring” is defined as the systematic sampling of air, water, soil, and biota in order to observe and study the environment, as well as to derive knowledge of this process. System is defined by the Oxford dictionary as “a set of things working together as parts of a mechanism or an interconnecting network; a complex whole.”. We can therefore define an “environmental monitoring system” (EMS) as a series of interconnected components that together enable the observation of the environment to obtain information that is useful for supporting decision making or policy definition aimed at addressing specific issues. Different scopes and type of environmental monitoring systems can be found in literature (Xu et al., 2014; Umar et al., 2015; Suter et al., 2006; Arbanas et al., 2014; Alippi et al., 2011) and can be focused on any of the five spheres of the Earth System that include the atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, lithosphere, and cryosphere (De Blij et al., 2005).

In the above proposed definition, we point the attention to the great importance that the scope of the EMS has: obtain useful information to tackle a problem. Therefore, the concept of transforming data into information is of primary concern in designing an “environmental monitoring system”. As an example of this process, we can think of how the value of rainfall in given locations and instants can be used to derive with a model when, where and how can we expect flooding. Karkouch et al. (2016) discussed the importance of data quality (DQ) in extracting information (insights) in Internet of Things (IoT) applications. This importance has been presented in many works (Berti-Equille, 2007, Hand et al., 2001 and Hipp et al., 2001) leading to the conclusion that DQ is a prerequisite to ensure valid results. Nevertheless, DQ is not the only parameter influencing the usefulness of an EMS, in fact gathering the right information at the right time is also essential to effectively support the decision-making (Belo, 2013).

As represented in Figure 1, the role of the EMS is to provide time series data, that together with other contextual resources (economic, social, etc.) can be processed to derive

information that permit to better understand the system. This is the starting point for taking actions that aided at manage the resource and take appropriate measures to reduce risks.

Figure 1 - Integrated design of Environmental Monitoring Systems(EMS) to support decision making and resource management

After Douglas et al. (2008) and Mineraud et al. (2016) we can decompose the architecture of a EMS in 6 different domains (see Figure 2):

- sensor domain, where individual devices observe and record observations;
- acquisition domain, where data gathered by the sensor are transmitted and stored in a data warehouse;
- data-management domain, where data and metadata are organized and made accessible for quality control and distribution;
- processing domain, where elaboration capabilities are required to extract the information are offered;
- application domain, where information is made accessible in the form of maps, diagrams and reports;
- user domain, where the user interacts with the representation of the information to support decision-making.

The 6 domains can then be grouped in 3 main layers:

- **hardware:** it is composed by the sensor domain, it has the role of observing the environment and it is individuated by the wireless sensor network (WSN) nodes;
- **communication:** it is composed by the acquisition domain, it has the role of transferring the data from the "field" to the "office" and it is individuated by the transmission protocols and media;

- **service:** it is composed by data management, processing, application and user domain; it has the role of creating and exploiting the information; it is generally characterized by a number of chained web services.

Figure 2 - Environmental Monitoring System architecture and its components' domains grouped in hardware (yellow), communication (green) and service layer (blue).

To design the whole system, different factors need to be carefully taken into consideration so that the objectives can be met. The next sections of this chapter will therefore illustrate the general 4ONSE objectives and the influencing factors. The chapter 2 will describe, with a dedicated section for each of the 3 layers, the selected design and the motivation that led to it.

1.1 Factors Influencing the System Design (4 pages)

Several are the drivers in designing an environmental monitoring system. In the next sections we'll describe those that are relevant for this project. It will permit to better identify how they can impact the design process (Valada et al., 2010; Aimad et al., 2016).

Reliability

The reliability is the capacity of the system to continue monitoring regardless of the failure of some of the stations. This factor is very important, in fact several are the causes that may compromise a station functioning: power failure, connectivity problems, physical damage, environment interference, etc. From a mathematical point of view, the reliability of a station R_s can be described in time by a Poisson distribution; the probability of a station not to register any failure in an interval $(0, t)$ can be therefore described by:

$$R_s(t) = e^{-\lambda_s t} \quad (1.1)$$

where:

λ_k is the failure rate of node k

t is the time period

Scalability

The capacity of the monitoring system to scale is very important, in fact the density and the number of stations could change in time, depending on specific needs driven by local requirements, like for instance a temporary densification due to an impending hazardous event. In addition, the size of archived data can extremely grow in time and thus more analysing power may be required to use these data. We can define scalability of the system as the capacity to accommodate an increasing size (station or data) without degrading the performance.

Costs

The cost of a monitoring system is important since it affects not only the set-up phase but also the maintenance during the years. The cost of a monitoring system is composed by several components and sub-components like the cost of: hardware, software, communication, and personnel. Moreover, the costs need to be evaluated in time, since the maintenance of the system have cost that may be relevant.

Hardware Constraints

The basic components of a monitoring system consist in monitoring stations and a data warehouse. The single monitoring station can be further decomposed in four elementary components: power unit, sensing unit, processing unit and transceiver. The data warehouse is composed by one receiver and one or more server unit. The server unit is then characterized by specific processors (CPU), memory (RAM), hard drives, network connection, video and power supply. Accessible market and budget might limit the hardware choice and put some physical limits.

Figure 3 - Basic hardware components of a monitoring system

Network Topology

The change in sensor locations (topology) can occur in one of the following three phases: deployments where the initial configuration is set; post-deployment where stations can be replaced due to failure or moved due to specific needs; and re-deployment where new stations are installed and included in the network. Spatial density and distance of sensor may influence the selection of the data transmission strategy.

Temporal resolution

Different physical monitored variables may have different smooth variations periods, intended as the interval occurred between two consecutive timestamps where a small (or none) variation, which can be considered negligible for the scope of the EMS, can be observed. This drives the selection of the sampling strategy.

Measures Accuracy

The degree to which the measure is close to the real values. The error theory (Taylor, 1997) defines that the measurement of a physical quantity can never be made with perfect accuracy, there will always be some error or uncertainty present. This uncertainty is composed by systematic and random errors. While systematic errors most commonly arise from defects in the instrumentation or from using improper measuring techniques, random errors are due to accidental and uncontrolled changing conditions like incorrect

sensor readings due to changes experimental conditions (humidity, vibrations, temperature, etc.). The true value, being unknown, can therefore only be associated with the most probable value. The accuracy can therefore be indicated only with the estimate of the experimental error which indicates how reliable the measures are. Accuracy, which impact the usefulness of the observations to address different issues, drives the selection of the sensor types.

Operating Environment

Depending on the location of the monitoring system deployment we can vary from an extremely hostile to a hospitable environment like as examples forests, oceans, disaster areas, battlefields, houses, developing countries, factories, etc. Different location may pose some requirements in terms of sensor tolerance, construction, communication options, etc.

Transmission Media

Stations communicate with each other and/or to the data warehouse through the use of transmission media which generally is wireless. Radio Frequency (RF) or infrared (IR) is usually used. Common used standard protocols are Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, ZigBee and GPRS.

Energy Consumption

A station has three main task to accomplish: sense data, process data and transmit data. It is therefore possible to subdivide the energy consumption in these three components. Generally, communication is the more energy consuming part and ist consume can be expressed by:

$$P_C = N_T[P_T(T_{on} + T_{st}) + P_{out}(T_{on})] + N_R[P_R(R_{on} + R_{st})]$$

Where:

- N_T is the number of times the transmitter is turned on per unit time.
- P_T is the power consumed by the transmitter.
- T_{on} is the transmitter on time.
- T_{st} is the transmitter startup time.
- P_{out} is the output power of the transmitter.
- N_R is the number of times the receiver is turned on per unit time.
- P_R is the power consumed by the receiver.
- R_{on} is the receiver on time.
- R_{st} is the receiver startup time.

Energy used for processing is in general small and can be controlled limiting it to essential tasks only. The consumption of sensing is more variable, depending on the sensor and

sampling method (continuous or discrete), but can be considered in general in between the other two components.

The energy consumption of the data warehouse is usually not a problem when the servers are hosted data centers; nevertheless, adequate power supply to backup possible electricity failure is required.

Monitoring scope

Different application has different data requirements in term of quality, aggregation, accessibility, update frequency, etc. Even if it is suggested to keep a broader view to permit the use of monitored data by as much application as possible, this aspect, together with other factors may influence the system design.

Data users

The number of expected users define the architecture of the information system. Many concurrent users could stress the capacity of the software system and cause a decrease of the performances and availability of the services.

Dimension of time series

The dimension of time series affects the architecture of the system both in the hardware and software component in terms of performance, disk space usage, maintenance and data protection.

Node deployment

A proper node deployment scheme can reduce the complexity of problems in WSNs as, for example, routing, data reporting frequency, communication, etc. Furthermore, it can extend the lifetime of WSNs by minimizing the energy consumption.

Data reporting method

They can be one or a mix of: time-driven, when data are transmitted at constant periodic time intervals; event-driven, when sensor nodes react immediately to the occurrence of a certain event; query-driven, when sensor nodes respond to a query generated by another component of the network.

Data fault tolerance

It enables a system to continue its operation without losing data or connection thanks to a storing and logging strategy. The fault-tolerance has a key role for the reliability and creditability of EMS.

Data aggregation

It is the combination of data according to a certain aggregation function (e.g. duplicate suppression, minima, maxima and average). This technique has been used to achieve energy efficiency and data transfer optimization.

Security

In order to build a trusted system some security issues must be considered. These include how to protect communications, how to manage authentication and access control to resources in systems that may consist of thousands of devices and how to ensure integrity and confidentiality of the data in the system.

Quality of service

According to the INSPIRE Network Services Performance Guidelines the quality of a web service is defined as the capacity to «include performance, reliability, scalability, capacity, robustness, exception handling, accuracy, integrity, accessibility, availability, interoperability, security, and network-related QoS requirements». Is therefore the capacity to provide responses in a reasonable quick time under different stressing conditions (number of concurrent users) and to provide a stable service with very low down-time».

Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability of different information technology systems and software applications to communicate, exchange data, and use the information that has been exchanged. This is often achieved by means of definition of standards, which define the formats and the rules to access and interpret the data.

Data quality

As defined in Wikipedia «Data quality refers to the condition of a set of values of qualitative or quantitative variables. There are many definitions of data quality but data is generally considered high quality if it is "fit for [its] intended uses in operations, decision making and planning"». This is verified by a number of Quality Control procedures (QC) as defined for example in the "Guidelines on Quality Control Procedures for Data from

Automatic Weather Stations” of the WMO. In Wireless Sensor networks (WSN), data quality can be decomposed in several dimensions which are commonly defined like accuracy, confidence, completeness, volume, timeliness; or are specific for the IoT like the ease of access, access security, interpretability, duplicates, and availability.

Software openness

The software rights are regulated by means of licenses. A license can be considered as Open Source when it guarantees the user the right to freely access the source code and grant him the right to study, modify and redistribute the code without any restriction. On the opposite, proprietary software licenses generally grant the user just the right to use the software under major restrictions and payment of a fee. In proprietary software the source code is almost always keep secret and only binary files are accessible.

2 Material and Methods

This chapter, after a section that describes the 4nse general requirements, introduces for each of the layer described in Chapter 1 (hardware, communication and service) four sections that discuss the layer structure, the influencing factors and requirements, the state of the art, and the selected design.

2.1 System requirements

As reported by Hill (2003) general environmental monitoring systems aim at collecting sensor readings from different locations in order to detect trends and interrelations. Most of the applications are designed to collect data along a period and then analyse them offline to extract trends or forecasts. Most of the applications requires that the collected series are acquired at regular steps and at fixed location in time.

From the monitoring perspective, it is generally required to have a large number of stations that regularly collect and send data to a central data warehouse using traditional methods. Long time series are mostly desired, and thus long network lifetime is required. The sensors are in average evenly located in space, but specific hot-point may be additionally monitored. In environmental application, due to its stationary requirement of series, in general it is not necessary to have a dynamic routing strategy. Depending on monitoring target area size and sensor density it is possible to pre-calculate and implement transmission strategies that minimize the costs and data transmission failure, taking advantage of *gateways* (interface between the application platform and the wireless nodes) and *relay nodes* or "routers" (nodes used to extend network coverage acting as a bridge to the gateway) which are connected to *leaf nodes* (physical interface between the network and the sensors/actuators it is wired to). For many scenarios, the transmission intervals can be in the order of minutes or hours. Typical reporting is expected to be between 10 and 30 minutes since monitored variables such as temperature, humidity, wind and rainfall do not change so quickly to need higher reporting rates. Due to the long lifetime requirements, a precise synchronization is essential since appropriate cycles of sleep mode and transmission have to be programmed to save energy. Also no strict latency limits are required since moderate delays in sample transmission do not significantly affect applications. Nodes are expected to fail in time, so periodic system reconfiguration, replacements and maintenance is envisioned. Self-energy sustaining of nodes should be guaranteed at maximum, and in case of sustainable energy powers it should guarantee the function along 5 days of unfavourable conditions (i.e.: cloud days for solar panels).

In summary, the most important characteristics of an environmental network that should be met are:

- long lifetime

- precise synchronization,
- low data rates
- relatively static topology
- moderate data delay admitted

In addition to the above listed characteristics, the 4ONSE project is expecting to design and develop a system which is:

- based on Open Hardware and Open Software
- composed by non-conventional and low-cost sensing technologies
- compliant with international Open Standards
- capable to handle massive dataset as Open Data

These four pillars will drive all the design choices and will constitute the mainstream of the design process. Moreover, taking into considerations the outcomes of the kick-off meeting with the stakeholders that individuated the management of the artificial basins and floods risk reduction as the main concerns of the government agencies, the system should be designed to target this application. As a result, the following characteristics are also required:

- good data quality
- high quality of services.

Other desired characteristics of the system, identified discussing with the stakeholders, are:

- modular solution to better fit different needs
- ability to support different sensors,
- alternative data collection methods (automatic or manual),
- different level of installation protection,
- ease of use and maintenance.

The environmental parameters to be monitored to accomplish the individuated applications are all the standard meteorological variables:

- air temperature,
- relative humidity,
- barometric pressure,
- solar radiation,
- wind speed and direction,
- rainfall.

Additionally, the following parameters could optionally be monitored:

- soil moisture,
- station position,
- water level.

In order to monitor the single station and support its management, internal system parameters like battery level and internal temperature should also be measured.

2.2 Hardware Layer

Layer description

The network nodes are the fundamental components of the EMS which are responsible to interact with the physical world that it ultimately desires to monitor and/or control. Every single node is composed by a hardware platform which should provide at minimum:

- Management of node configuration
- Scheduling and execution of measurement tasks
- Signal condition and data acquisition for different sensors
- Temporary storage of data (data and configurations)
- Scheduling and execution of communication and networking tasks
- Transmission of data packets

Additionally, if the node act as a *relay node* (bridge between other nodes and the gateway) it may need to provide also:

- Reception and forwarding of data packets
- Advanced processing capabilities
- Alert generation

As illustrated in Figure 4, the basic units of a node and the corresponding tasks are identified by:

- Processing: this unit is responsible for coordinating the scheduling and execution of all the node tasks and locally store data and configurations.
- Sensor: this unit is responsible for interfacing the sensor and collect the measure signal.
- Transceiver: this unit enable the transmission (and eventually reception) of data packages.
- Power: this unit is dedicated to provide sufficient energy to sustain the node.

Figure 4 - Basic units of a monitoring network node.

Processing unit

Depending on the type of node it may rely on embedded devices or a more powerful computer and may need to provide all or part of the functions listed. Embedded devices can be classified in microcontrollers and micro-PC. A microcontroller is a single integrated circuit that has on chip a fixed amount of CPU, RAM, I/O, ROM, timer and serial port. It is generally characterized by the ability to: run a single program at a time, have low power consumption, have low processing speed, have low cost. A micro-PC is composed by a microprocessor, which has integrated the CPU only, and various peripherals externally connected (RAM, storage, network adapters, etc.). It is characterized by the ability to: host operating system, run multi-threads processes, have access to complex peripherals up to desired limits, and have high processing speed.

Sensor unit

The sensor unit is composed by a number of transducers (devices that convert a physical quantity into an electrical signal) connected with the processing unit. According to (Baronti et al., 2007) two main approaches have been followed in designing transducers. The first approach has been introduced by the Crossbow Technology Inc. (<http://www.xbow.com>) and is based on the integration of a number of transducers on a board that can then be connected with the processing unit. Typical "transducer boards" (or shield) may provide a combination of several transducers like ambient light, temperature, humidity, sounder, microphone, accelerometers, etc. The latter approach was followed by the Moteiv Corporation (<http://www.moteiv.com>) and conceived to directly put the transducers on the node board. This solution is clearly less flexible but reduces production costs.

Transceiver

The transceiver is a device which incorporates in a single package transmitter and receiver. Through it, a node communicates with other units enabling “near” real-time monitoring. While optical communication is cheap, consume low energy and has low costs, the constraint of inter-visibility is very hard to meet in the field. For this reason almost all the implemented solutions rely on Radio frequency (RF) communication. Different frequencies identify different applications. The most used protocols are Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, ZigBee and GPRS.

Power unit

Mikhaylov and Tervonen (2011) listed the power supply options used by network nodes:

- Power supply from electrical grid using AC/DC converters
- Batteries or accumulators
- Energy form environment harvesting system with capacitive storage
- A combination of the above listed options.

The first option does not put any limitation in the energy consumption, and therefore is preferred whenever is possible and particularly in nodes with high duties cycle (routers, access points, etc.). Since the voltage required by the node is in general in the order of 5-15 V DC, an external AC/DC adapter is used for getting the right supply.

When direct supply is not accessible, the usage of rechargeable or not rechargeable batteries is a common used option. This option has power capacitance limited by the battery type, environment parameters (e.g. temperature) and node consumption. Sometime is possible to associate with the battery a capacitor which buffers the energy consumed in peak load periods.

The third option, applies the so called power scavenging techniques (Deorankar and Markande, 2014) which helps in providing unlimited energy for the lifespan of the electronic device extracting it from the ambient environment (sunlight, mechanical energy, thermal energy, and RF energy). Among the possible energy power sources, the solar cells are the most used due to its highest power density and wide availability. This solar harvesting solution is generally composed by a solar panel, an input regulator, an energy storage and an output regulator (Shaikh and Zeadally, 2016). Several factors may influence the efficiency and therefore need to be carefully considered in power unit design: characteristics of the panel, size and position, capacity of the batteries, operating conditions (changing weather), ageing effects of the panel (Raghunathan et al., 2005; Saggini et al., 2010).

State of the art

Several examples of different hardware layers are presented in literature regarding weather station nodes (WS-node). In the next paragraphs a selection of them is shortly presented.

Chebbi et al. (2011) presented a weather station node designed for irrigation scheduling in developing countries. The solution selected the PIC microcontroller for processing, an Xbee module for communication and 16-pins socket for expander sensors board connection. A 3V3 regulator is used to supply the node. The WS-node is powered with a 6V, 4Ah rechargeable battery regulated with a 6V, 135mA solar panel. The selected transducers are: SHT75 to measure temperature (accuracy of ± 0.3 °C and operating range -40 to +125 °C) and humidity (accuracy of ± 1.8 % and operating range 0 to 100%); Davis solar radiation to measure solar radiation with 1.67mV per W/m² resolution; Tipping bucket rain gauge with 0.28 mm of resolution for precipitation; ADS anemometer with 3 cup rotor measuring wind speed in the range of 5 –200 Km/h; ADS vane with reed switches each 45 degrees to measure wind direction.

Rao, et.al (2016) have developed an embedded device using Arduino UNO board (ATmega328 microprocessor) with ESP8266 Wi-Fi transceiver for communication. No specific power unit has been specified and direct power via USB is provided. Monitoring parameters and relative transducers are: LM35 to measure temperature (accuracy of ± 0.5 °C and operating range -55 to +150 °C); MQ-7 to measure Carbon monoxide (CO) from 20 to 2000ppm; Light-Dependent Resistor (LDR) sensor to measure light intensity; LMV321 sound detector to measure sound pressure levels up to 90 Db.

Ram and Gupta (2016) developed an IoT based data logger for weather monitoring. This system, is very similar to that proposed by Rao et al. (2016) in the observed parameters (temperature, CO₂, humidity and light intensity) and in communication transceiver (ESP8266). The selected board is LPC 2148 that has a ARM7TDMI microcontroller with 512K on-chip memory.

Saini et al. (2016) proposed a solution based on Arduino Uno Board and the Zigbee wireless device. The transducers are: SHT25 to measure humidity with a typical accuracy of ± 1.8 % and an operational range 0 to 100 %; BMP180 to measure air pressure (up to 0.03hPa resolution) and temperature (accuracy ± 2 °C and operational range -40 to 85 °C); anemometer and wind vane based on reed switches to measure wind speed and direction. In addition, this system includes LED to display monitored values.

Kanagaraj et al (2015) presented a system deployed in Malaysia to monitor weather and environmental conditions using a commercial solution. The hardware is composed by the ēKo Weather Station which does not provide details on the used transducers but list the observed variables with relative resolution (ϵ), range (ρ) and accuracy (σ). It measures barometric pressure ($\epsilon = 0.1$ mbar, $\rho = 880$ to 1080 mbar, $\sigma = 1.0$ mbar), rainfall ($\epsilon = 0.02$

mm, $\rho = 0$ to 9999 mm/day, $\sigma = 4\%$), solar radiation ($\varepsilon = 1$ W/m², $\rho = 0$ to 1800 W/m², $\sigma = 5\%$), temperature ($\varepsilon = 0.1$ °C, $\rho = -40$ to 65 °C, $\sigma = 0.5\%$), humidity ($\varepsilon = 1\%$, $\rho = 0$ to 100%, $\sigma = 3\%$), wind direction ($\varepsilon = 1^\circ$, $\rho = 0^\circ$ to 360°, $\sigma = 7^\circ$) and wind speed ($\varepsilon = 0.1$ m/s, $\rho = 1$ to 67 m/s, $\sigma = 5^\circ$). Energy was provided by solar panels and data transmitted every 15 minutes using the proprietary ©XMesh radio protocol.

van de Giesen et al. (2014) describe the first generation stations of the Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO) project. The station is composed by a funnel of 10 cm diameter and optical drip counter to measure rainfall. Temperature is measured with 0.5 °C accuracy and solar radiation with 7% over a range of 0-1500 W/m². Ultrasonic transducer measures the wind speed with 0.3 m/s accuracy over a range of 0-10 m/s and 3% for higher speed. Wind direction is detected with $\pm 3^\circ$ and barometric pressure with ± 1 kPa. The power is provided by six AA batteries fed by a 3×7 cm² solar panel. Communication is provided by GSM. Level, compass and GPS provide additional information for quality checks.

Chemin et al. (2014; 2015) presented a weather station system based on open source hardware (OSHW) based on Arduino board produced in Sri Lanka and named *Lakduino*. The sensor unit is composed by ©SparkFun Weather Meters (Wind Vane with 22.5° resolution, Cup Anemometer, Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge with 0.28 mm resolution) that is connected to a weather shield integrating Humidity/Temperature Sensor (HTU21D, accuracy $\pm 3\%$), Barometric Pressure (MPL3115A2, accuracy = ± 0.4 kPa) and Light Sensor (ALS-PT19). A GPS unit (GP-635T based on uBlox chipset) is also connected with the weather shield to retrieve timestamp and position. Open data logger is used to locally store the measures on an SD card. The power unit is composed by solar panel (20W) and a battery (12V,7AH). A GPS module is also connected to send SMS in case of high rainfall rates detected. The total hardware costs have been estimated in about 350 USD.

Influencing factors and requirements

The main influencing factors for the design of the hardware layer are:

- Costs
- Transmission media
- Energy consumption
- Accuracy of the measurements
- Market accessibility to devices
- Operating environment
- System openness

The definition of a budget drives the overall design and selection of the components for the hardware. Nevertheless, within the defined costs different solutions can be envisaged.

A priority of needs should be defined so that the selection could try to optimize the solution. Energy consumption is often the limiting factors, so this aspect should be carefully considered particularly when selecting the transmission media which is the main drain source. Also operating environment and desired accuracy are constraints that can limit the choice of the transducers. The selection of locally made parts is preferential and market availability is a strong limit to guarantee maintenance and sustainability. The level of system openness can also drive same choice.

Design

Selection of the processing unit

Due to the requirement of Open Hardware platform, the selection is guided to one of the Arduino boards available on the market. The **Arduino MEGA** has been selected because compared with other boards it offers more connectivity and memory at a similar cost (in Sri Lanka RS1500 ~10USD): 16 analog inputs and 54 digital input/output pins and 256 Kb of flash memory. See <https://www.arduino.cc/en/Products/Compare> for more details.

Figure 5 - Arduino MEGA board.

Selection of the sensor unit

WMO (2014) defines the operational measurement uncertainty requirements and instrument performance of in measuring meteorological variables. Following the listed properties that the 4ONSE system aims at measuring (see chapter 2.1) the relative WMO requirements are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 - WMO specifications for property measurements

Variable	Range	Resolution	Obs. type	Uncertainties	Time-constant	Averaging time
air temperature	-80 to +60 °C	0.1 K	Instant	0.3 K for ≤ -40 °C 0.1 K for > -40 °C and $\leq +40$ °C 0.3 K for $> +40$ °C	20 s	1 min

Relative humidity	0 – 100%	1%	Instant	1%	20 s	1 min
Atmospheric pressure	500 – 1080 hPa	0.1 hPa	Instant	0.1 hPa	2s	1 min
Wind speed	0 – 75 m s ⁻¹	0.5 m s ⁻¹	Auto	0.5 m s ⁻¹ for ≤ 5 m s ⁻¹ 10% for > 5 m s ⁻¹		
Wind direction	0 – 360°	1°	Auto	5°	Damping ratio > 0.3	2 and/or 10 min
Precipitation Intensity	0.02 mm h ⁻¹ – 2000 mm h ⁻¹	0.1 mm h ⁻¹	Instant	0.02 – 0.2 mm h ⁻¹ 0.1 mm h ⁻¹ for 0.2 – 2 mm h ⁻¹ 5% for > 2 mm h ⁻¹	< 30 s	1 min
Net radiation (daily)	Not specified	1 J m ⁻²	Total	0.4 MJ m ⁻² for ≤ 8 MJ m ⁻² 5% for > 8 MJ m ⁻²	20 s	daily

Similarly, a non-conventional but not open platform like the “Davis vantage pro2™ plus” for the cost of about 1000 USD has the specifications reported in Table 2.

Table 2 – Parameter specification for the “Davis vantage pro2™ plus” weather station

Variable	Range	Resolution	Obs. type	Uncertainties	Time-constant	Averaging time
air temperature	-40 to +65 °C	0.1 °C	Instant	0.3°C	10 s	n/a
Relative humidity	0 – 100%	1%	Instant	2%	50 s	n/a
Atmospheric pressure	540 – 1100 hPa	0.1 hPa	Instant	0.3 hPa	2s	15 min
Wind speed	0 – 89 m s ⁻¹	0.4 m s ⁻¹	Instant	0.5 m s ⁻¹ or 5%	3s	1 min
Wind direction	0 – 360°	1°	Instant	3°	3s	10 min
Precipitation Intensity	0 – 999.8 mm	0.2 mm h ⁻¹	Total	±4% or 0.02 mm < 100 mm h ⁻¹	n/a	15 min
Net radiation (daily)	0 to 1800 W/m ²	1 W m ⁻²	Total	5%	1 min	daily

Taking into consideration the accuracies and ranges of Table 2 and Table 9 the following sensor have been selected as transducers candidate:

Air temperature

Temperature is a common and important parameter usually measured for a wide range of weather related applications. The selection of the type of transducer depends on the accuracy and the range required. The most common sensor types and their characteristics are listed below in Table 5.

Table 3 - Commonly used temperature sensor types; Sources: Acromag Incorporated (2011) and Microstar Laboratories (2008)

Sensor type	Range (°C)	Accuracy (°C)	Output type	Comments
Negative Temperature Coefficient (NTC) thermistor	-50 to 250	High 0.05 to 1.5	Analog, exponential	Fast
Resistance Temperature Detector (RTD)	-200 to 600	High 0.1 to 1	Analog, exponential	Moderate speed
Thermocouple	-200 to 1750	low, 0.5 to 5	Analog, non-linear	Widest range, moderate speed
Semiconductor-based sensors	-70 to 150	Low/high 1 to 5	Analog/digital, linear	Low cost, slow speed

Considering the costs and accuracies of the different technologies we have selected the DS18B20 and the DHT22 as possible candidate, in particular the DS18B20 due to its waterproof characteristics is well suited for external positioning. In Table 4, the comparison of both sensors is shown.

Table 4 - Comparison of the DS18B20 and the DHT22 sensors.

	DS18B20	DHT22
Range	-55°C to +125°C	-40°C to 125°C
Accuracy	0.5°C (from -10°C to +85°C)	±0.2°C
Resolution	0.0625 °C	n.a.
Operating Voltage	3.0V to 5.5V DC	3.3V – 6V DC
Output	Digital	Digital (single-bus)
Response Time	750 ms	2 seconds
Note	Impermeable	none
Cost	USD 3	USD 5

Air humidity

The three main types of humidity sensors include ceramic sensing materials sensors, semiconducting sensors and polymer-based sensors. The most widely used sensor type is semiconductor sensing humidity sensors (Chen, 2005). Table 7 shows the comparison of most commonly used humidity sensors.

Table 5: Comparison HR202, DHT11 and DHT22 sensors. Source: DHT11 temperature and humidity module datasheet (2017), Humidity sensitivity resistor product manual (2017) and temperature & humidity module AM2302 product manual (2017)

	HR202	DHT11	DHT22	BME280
Range	20% to 95%	20% to 90%	0.0% to 99.9%	0% to 100%
Accuracy	±5%	±5%	±2%	±3%
Resolution				0.008%
Operating Voltage	1.5V AC	3.0V to 5.5V	3.3V to 5.5V	1.7V to 3.3V
Output	Analog, 19.8-50.2kΩ	Digital	Digital, 16-bit	Digital
Response Time	<10 seconds	6 – 30 seconds	<5 seconds	1 second
Cost	USD 10	USD 2	USD 5	USD 5

Considering the accuracies and resolution suggested by the WMO and that offered by the low cost sensors, together with the result of a test comparing different humidity sensors (<https://www.kandrsmith.org/RJS/Misc/hygrometers.html>) the BME280 has been selected. It clearly showed to be the most accurate at the specified 25°C and the most repeatable sensor.

Barometric pressure

A listing for pressure sensors, manufacturers, and a technical comparison between both piezo-resistive and capacitive pressure sensors can be found in Fragiacomio (2012). The Table 6 lists some of the sensors available on the market and used in applications listed in the state of the art. While MD-PS0002 have a range of measure out of the scope of atmospheric pressure measurement (~1000 hPa at sea level) the other sensors are quite similar. Since the BME280 has been already candidate for measuring air humidity it has been selected to monitor barometric pressure too.

Table 6 - Specifications of considered for pressure sensors

	BME280	MPL3115A2	BMP280	MD-PS002
Range	300 to 1100 hPa	500 to 1100 hPa	300 to 1100 hPa	1000 to 7000 hPa
Accuracy	±1 hPa	±4 hPa	±1 hPa	±0.2 FS
Resolution	0.2 Pa	0.25 Pa	0.01 hPa	5
Operating Voltage	1.71 to 3.6 V	3.0V to 5.5V	5V	Analog
Output	I2C	I2C	I2C	Analog
Cost	USD 5	USD 12	USD 10	2.5 USD

Wind speed and direction

The instrument for measuring wind speed is the anemometer while for measuring the wind direction is the wind vane. The most diffused technology for wind speed measurements is the mechanical three cups anemometer which mounts hemispherical cups on three horizontal arms mounted on a vertical shaft. Measuring the rotation rate it is possible to calculate the wind speed. Other more complicated and expensive solutions are ultrasonic anemometers which measure wind speed based on the time of flight of sonic pulses between pairs of transducers. Wind vane is moved to minimize the air resistance and pointed by prevailing winds in the wind direction. Magnetic switches detect for both the mechanical instruments the rotating speed and the direction. Quality of the materials and number of switches may define different quality and cost of the sensors.

Plastic solutions like the SEN-08942 (70 USD, 2.4 km/h = 1 switch/second for speed; 22.5 resolution for directions) have been used in literature even if do not comply with the WMO requirements. Nevertheless, it may require more replacements and maintenance work to guarantee the quality of the measures.

Precipitation Intensity

The standard instrument for the measurement of rainfall is the 203 mm (8 inch) rain gauge. In modern automatic weather stations a Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge (TBRG) is employed, which also has an aperture of 203 mm. There are two advantages of this type of rain gauge. Firstly, it never needs to be emptied, and secondly the amount of rainfall (and even the rate at which the rain is falling) can be read automatically. An electronic pulse is generated each time the volume of water collected in one of the small brass buckets causes the bucket to tip. This is equivalent to 0.2 mm of precipitation. The tipping bucket is made of specially formulated plastic for low surface tension to give quick and complete drain off of the collected rain. The main issues with tipping buckets is that with snow or ice precipitation they do not measure well and that with heavy rainfall (> 35 mm/h) they underestimate quantities.

The selected instrument is the "Davis Instruments Rain Collector for Perception and Wizard Stations, 0.01" that costs approximately 100 USD. This pluviometer has a collector of 16.5 cm diameter and 24 cm high and the resolution is 0.2 mm. The accuracy is $\pm 4\%$ of total or 0.2mm up to 50 mm/h, $\pm 5\%$ of total or 0.2mm up to 100 mm/h whichever is greater. The range is from 0.0 to 999.8 mm/day.

The option of locally create a rain gauge sensor is an option to be investigated.

Light sensor and net radiation

Ambient light covers three different spectrum components such as infrared, visible light and ultraviolet. Instead of measuring three different components separately, with this weather station light intensity is measured. Light measurements could be carried out simply by using LDR, photodiode or phototransistor. LDRs are always less sensitive than photo junctions and also they are slow in response. There is no simple conversion from the measured Lux to irradiation since it depends on the wavelength or color of the light. However, for the SUN, an approximate conversion of 0.0079 W/m² per Lux is applied (Islam and Hasan, 2016). Since the BH1750 is one of the most advanced sensors that can be used in robotics to measure the light and it is available in the Sri Lankan market it has been selected. Accuracies and precision of the sensor with respect to the WMO requirements has to be yet tested and verified.

Table 7 - Specifications of the BH1750FVI module.

Parameter	Value
Range (lux)	1 - 65535
Accuracy (%)	0.96 - 1.44 times, Sensor out / Actual lx, EV = 1000 lx, see datasheet
Operating Voltage (V)	2.4 - 3.6
Output	Digital, 16-bit, Serial output
Response Time	< 300 ms
Interface	I ² C
Peak wave length	560 nm
Cost	LKR 750.00

Selection of the transceiver unit

The communication depends on the network topology and the single station location. As discussed in the communication layer two type of media has been selected: WiFi and GPRS.

For the first solution we selected the ESP8266 as hardware component to provide a WiFi connection. The ESP8266 WiFi Module is a self-contained SOC with integrated TCP/IP protocol stack that can give any microcontroller access to the WiFi network. The ESP8266 is capable of either hosting an application or offloading all Wi-Fi networking functions from another application processor. Each ESP8266 module comes pre-programmed with an AT command set firmware, meaning. In addition, the ESP8266 module is an extremely cost effective board with a huge community and offers different way to improve the energy consumption of the system.

For the second solution encompassing the ability to use the GPRS connection we selected the SIM800 or SIM900 since both are compatible. Both the devices can be operated worldwide because they can operate in all four GSM bands used across the world. With

respect to SIM900 the SIM800 is available on the Sri Lankan market, is cheaper and has more functionalities (e.g.: Bluetooth) and therefore is the preferred choice.

Selection of the power unit

According to the state of the art and with the idea of making the sensors as much independent as possible the solar cells are selected as energy power source. The dimensioning the power system strongly depends on the consumption of the whole hardware layer. The best approach to power used by the system is to monitor the voltage and current with an amp-meter. At this stage, where the prototype has not been yet implemented, it is possible to determine approximate estimations.

We can use the general rule of having at least a solar panel producing 2/3 time the power consumption of the system. With a conservative hypothesis of system consumption of 150 mA and a supplied current voltage of 12V, the daily power consumption can be estimated at 43.2 Wh ($0.15A * 12V * 24h$). The daily power production of the solar panel can be assessed multiplying the panel power by the expected hours of sunshine in a day and a power loss factor along the chain assumed to be 40%. So, for an average of 6 hours of sun in a day, a 30W panel can produce 108 Wh.

If we use the panel to fully sustain the system, we can have from the panel 64.8 Wh extra to recharge the battery, that divided by 12V gives 5.4 Ah in a day. To fully recharge the battery in a completely dried situation it will take about 1.3 days, and considering that battery will last much longer if it is not fully discharged the system should be able to fully recharge in one day.

The above estimation does not consider overcasting or mostly cloudy conditions where the solar panel produce only the 10-25% of their rated capacity. In Figure 6 the Sri Lanka cloud cover statistics are illustrated: the median cloud cover percentage has a variation along the year ranging from a minimum of 39% to a maximum of 62%.

Considering the assumption above, the selected solar power system to be tested and adapted in the prototype testing phase is composed by:

- 30W Solar Panel
- 12V, 22Ah rechargeable battery
- Solar charger
- Power Regulator

Figure 6 - Cloud cover types and median cloud cover for Colombo, Sri Lanka (source: <https://weatherspark.com>)

Weather station schema

According to the selected hardware components, the schema of the proposed weather station is shown in Figure 7.

fritzing

Figure 7 - Schema of the proposed weather station.

Hardware layer integration

The sensor node has been initially designed as illustrated in Figure 8. After system prototyping and testing new designs can be implemented to fulfill different needs and requirements. In the proposed design, the hardware has been physically separated in 3 main panels: power supply, sensor connection and main. The power supply panel is connected with the solar panel which is fixed on a rotating and inclinable support to optimize its solar exposition. The power supply contains the solar controller and the battery and it gives power to the other two panels. All the external sensors are plugged into the sensor connection panel through pin connectors for easy sensor removal and replacement. The main panel contains: Arduino Mega2560 controller, SIM800 GSM module, GPS and SD card, main power regulator, local regulator for module power, LCD for in-situ display, fan controller and fan, RTC module and other supportive circuitry.

Figure 8 - Sketch of hardware layer integration

The approximate cost of the hardware layer is approximately 500 USD, its components and the specific costs are illustrated in Table 8.

Table 8 - List of hardware components and approximate costs

Item	Place of purchase	Cost in USD
Power supply unit		

30W Solar Panel with solar charger	Local market	50
12V, 22Ah Rechargeable battery	Local market	20
Sensor connection panel		
DS18B20 temperature sensor	Local market	3
BME280 humidity and pressure sensor	Ebay	5
SEN-08942 wind speed, wind direction + shipping cost	Sparkfun	76+40
Davis rain collector	Davis	100
BH1750 Digital Light sensor	Local market	5
Main controller		
Arduino Mega4560	Local market	20
OpenLog SD card	Local market	10
SIM800 GPRS Module	Local market	20
Mounting pole		
Stand	Local market	54
Other		
Boxes	Local market	40
Wires	Local market	10
Protectors	Local market	10
Total cost		USD 463
Miscellaneous costs – Power regulator, printed circuit boards, concreting the mounting pole base (if needed) – 5%	Local market	USD 19
Aggregate cost		USD 482

2.3 Service Layer

Layer description

According to D’Anca et al. (2017), a data management platform (DMP) solution is important to collect, validate and distribute data ensuring fast navigation and access to the data/metadata stored. The platform must be efficient, secure and interoperable to provide a set of high-level services such as the decision support systems (DSS) for supporting decision makers in managing emergency situations due to natural hazards. Its architecture is generally composed by 5 layers: data receiver, data storage, data analysis and data viewer (Figure 9).

This chain of interconnected layers is feed by numeric observations that are detected in the field by the hardware layer (WSN nodes) and received thanks to the communication layer (see chapter 2.4) by means of one of the available technologies.

The data receiver layer is the first component of a DMP. Usually, it is a software hosted on a server with methods to collect data, convert formats, perform simple validation and forward data into the data storage layer. This layer need to fulfil the data input requirements in term of size and transmission frequency.

Figure 9 - Schema of the data management platform.

The data storage layer is composed by a database whose architecture should be able to support a large amount of data and requests: the big data challenge. Big data are often described using the so called five “v” (Demchenko et al., 2014): volume, velocity, variety, veracity and value. Volume refers to the vast amounts of data generated; Velocity refers to the speed at which new data is generated; Variety refers to the different types of data; Veracity refers to the messiness or trustworthiness of the data; Value refers to the capacity of using big data to derive a value. In an EMS, at the service layer level, the volume challenge is to support both a large number of connected nodes and extremely long and high frequency time series. Moreover, very high observation frequency requires fast insertion of data (velocity), different configuration of nodes leads to heterogeneous data types (variety), the data quality is a main concern to correctly support decision making (veracity), the ability to convert data into information is the main objective of the EMS (value).

According to Yang et al. (2017) there are many solutions to efficient handle the Big Data such as massive parallel processing, distributed databases, data-mining grids, scalable storage systems and advanced computing architectures. Nevertheless, in selecting a storage unit for EMS we have to consider that, due to its frequent importance in reducing losses, it should guarantee the data robustness, consistency and availability as well as the so called ACID properties (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, Durability) (Gray et al., 1992) that assure the quality to the database transactions.

The data analysis is the third link of the DMP chain. It has the objectives of executing complex data validation (e.g.: temporal and spatial coherence) and aggregation, extracting information, and preparing data for end-users. In particular, the data validation process is of primary importance since from the quality of the data may depend the correctness of the extracted information.

The data visualisation is the last layer. It provides data visualization and human interaction for data exploration and analysis that enable wise decision-making and research analysis. For example, in the context of natural risk mitigation, this layer can be an early-warning system with a set of useful tools to visualize maps and model forecasting that support the planning and implementation of civil protection actions. Within this layer, the metadata

management is also usually supported to provide to the user significant complementary information about data such as sources, methods, uncertainties etc.

All the above mentioned layers are essentially software components hosted on a server machine. As a consequence, the server configuration may affect the overall performance of the layer. The costs are generally the main driver in the selection of hardware resources but in order to guarantee adequate quality of the services the software requirements in terms of RAM, bandwidth and CPU should also be carefully considered.

State of the art

In the literature, several different solutions are reported. The above presented layer has been implemented either with proprietary or open source solutions. We have found that we can distinguish between two main categories of data management: conventional system based expensive software and hardware and non-conventional system based on low-cost software and hardware. After the evaluation of several examples, we have selected three exhaustive examples that showed the best practice in real world applications in term of robustness, availability and innovation.

Among the conventional systems we selected the MeteoSwiss monitoring system from Switzerland (www.meteoswiss.ch) and the United Kingdom's Meteorological Monitoring System (MMS) of the Met Office (www.metoffice.gov.uk) national weather service. As a representative of non-conventional system we selected the SnowFort open source WSN (Liao et al., 2014).

Currently, MeteoSwiss with the SwissMetNet project reaches the number of 160 automatic monitoring stations. These stations deliver a multitude of current data on the weather and climate in Switzerland every ten minutes. The data management layer architecture is composed by three stages: staging area, data storage and data analysis. Before entering in the staging area the data, coming from different sources, are received, checked, transformed and integrated. In the staging area a number of data quality checks and error detection processes are executed to polish the data which are then stored in the data storage. Here the right data to be elaborated for supporting the decision making can be found. Using these data number of processing and data analysis tools are available to extract and to present information and results that are directly consumed by decision-makers. In synthesis, each automatic station is equipped with an Automatic Data Acquisition System (ADAS) which performs the measurements and collects, pre-processes and transmits the data to a central data acquisition system. After this process, the Central Data Acquisition System and the Network and Instrument Monitoring and Data Analyzing System (CDAS/NIMDAS) polls the data from the stations and performs a first quality control to detect instrumental problems. The data are finally transmitted to the Data warehouse (DWH) (Tombros, 2001). In this way, the observations flow a chain of 5

different levels. Data are controlled, analysed, processed with a steadily increasing degree of sophistication according to WMO recommendations (WMO, 1993). The first level of the chain regards the wireless sensor network where data are in a raw state. The other four levels are implemented inside the data management platform guaranteeing many grades of data aggregation (from one minute to monthly aggregation values) and control actions performed by specific software of the proprietary suite. The Quality Control tests suite is composed by 5 modules (Musa et al., 2003):

- the CC-module checks the consistency of the data coming in from the stations for a single observation term and calculates as well derived parameters;
- The PuMAB module verifies, once a day, the values using an enlarged set of tests including tests for temporal variability;
- The PuMIB tool for interactive processing has a graphical interface which presents the data on a spreadsheet as well as time series plots. Corrections can be performed on either representation;
- The VERA module is used for spatial plausibility tests with nearby stations to give information of the percentage of suspicious values, possible systematic errors, representativeness of a station;
- The tool THOMAS offers monthly data series using standardised methods.

The United Kingdom's Met Office is the other existing working solution chosen as an example of conventional monitoring systems. The Met Office network, called Meteorological Monitoring System (MMS), has 280 automatic weather stations and the entire system is supplied by an external company. The system provides high resolution observations (one minute) and a central system to monitor and control the data based on the proprietary suite SCOPE-X. In the MMS, the high resolution data are maintained and stored due to the possible interest of researchers, forecasters and quality control staff. As in the MeteoSwiss architecture, data are aggregates into a variety of frequencies according to the WMO recommendations. Before storing, data are evaluated and associated with a quality flag indicator. Afterwards, the system produces and transmits coded messages in the FM-12 format to a central server in Exeter. The FM-12, also called SYNOP (surface synoptic observations), is a numerical code used for reporting weather observations made by manned and automated weather stations. SYNOP reports are typically sent every six hours on short-wave and low frequency. A report consists of groups of numbers (and slashes where data is not available) describing general weather information, such as the temperature, barometric pressure and visibility at a weather station. It can be decoded by open-source software such as seaTTY, metaf2xml or Fldigi. All this procedure is done by the SCOPE-X proprietary software suite. It provides a fully scalable, flexible, expandable system for weather monitoring and observation solution. It consists of a real-time database, connected to an Oracle long-term historic database, and features flexible data interfaces. The core of the solution comprises two sets of central

server computers acting as a duty/standby pair located in primary and back-up computer halls. This arrangement ensures that if one server or computer hall has technical problems, the system will continue to operate seamlessly and data will remain available to downstream systems and users. MMS also contains a pair of database servers, providing a 12-month rolling archive of one-minute resolution data from all sensors at all sites, and web servers which enable desktop users to access information within the real time and historical databases. The central servers provide extensive data monitoring, automatic alarms, calculation of derived values from embedded and basic user-definable algorithms, and various facilities for implementing centralised automatic control. Statistical functions and consequential alarm generation are also standard features of the system (Green, 2010).

According to Liao et al. (2014), SnowFort is an open-source wireless sensor system designed for infrastructure and environmental monitoring. It provides functionalities useful to collect, cleanse, analyse and visualise real-time data. The SnowFort challenges were to develop a platform that can be durable, reliable, adaptable, simple and smart. The system architecture of the SnowFort wireless monitoring system has four parts: a wireless sensor mote, a base station, a cloud server and a web interface. The wireless mote is a sensor system battery-powered with the purpose of collecting, compressing and transmitting data (hardware and communication layers). Data are polled by the receiver base station. The receiver is a low cost Linux machine (Raspberry Pi) and has the capability to access the Internet via Ethernet, WLAN, cellular or satellite network. A python script implements a protocol communication to the motes and transmit data to the cloud server, the third part of the system. The infrastructure of this part implements the DSS built to handle the massive data flows and real-time process and visualisation. It is written in Python using the Flask framework. A web server using the HTTPS standard is developed with a RESTful service and the JSON format support. The data warehouse has two databases for storing raw data and cleansed real-time data which can be used by end-users. MySQL is chosen as the database software infrastructure and Python is used to implements standard API to give simple accessibility.

Influencing factors and requirements

The main influencing factors for the design of the service layer are:

- quality of service;
- data users;
- dimension of time series;
- interoperability;
- data quality;
- software openness.

The above list drives the development of the whole service layer. The service layer provides near-real-time access to environmental data with different accuracy, resolution and aggregation as well as outputs for different services, applications and users. A data management system has to promote the accessibility, the interoperability and the reusability. The choice of well-known standard protocols, services and formats drives the design of the service layer which has to offer environmental conditions with high performance and high availability.

Design

As previously discussed, the service layer must include a data receiver, a data storage, a data analyser and a data viewer. Due to the openness and interoperability requirements defined by the project the Sensor Observation Service (SOS) (OGC, 2007) from the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) has been selected as core standard service to implement the service layer. The SOS standard implements a series of requests to manage sensor networks and relative observations. The SOS standard offers the capabilities for registering new sensor, inserting data, requesting metadata, filtering and downloading observations. It is based on five key elements (Figure 10):

- **Observations:** they are the core element of the standard and represent the values measured at given time instants (e.g.: value: 0.2, time: 08-11-2012 12:12); they are represented according to the O&M standard data model.
- **Procedure:** indicates who provided the observations, this is generally the sensor but it may also be a generic process that leads to some observations (e.g.: node number 5); it is represented as SensorML standard data model.
- **Observed Properties:** they represent the phenomena that are observed (e.g.: air-temperature) and is represented with a URI (uniform resource identifier) referring to a selected ontology.
- **Feature of interest:** it is the feature that relates to the observations, so for an in-place instrument is the sensor location, while for remote device it is the target location (e.g.: location: Trevano, coordinates: 718345,99224,389, reference system: CH1903/LV03). It is represented according to the om:featureOfInterest element of the O&M standard.
- **Offering:** it is a collection of sensor used to conveniently group them up and expose data coverage (covered time interval, monitored area, observed phenomena, etc.). It is represented as sos:ObservationOffering element of the SOS standard.

SOS key objects

Figure 10 - Key objects of the SOS standard (source: www.istsos.org).

Among the available software implementation distributed with open source licences, the istSOS (Istituto Scienze della Terra Sensor Observation Service) has been selected due to its specific features designed to manage the data management chain of hydro-climatic data. In fact, it is currently used as data management platform to monitor the Verbano lake and to collect hydro-meteorological data of the Canton Ticino (Cannata et al., 2013).

The istSOS software is composed by a server and a client side. The server side of the application is entirely written in Python (Van Rossum, 2003) and relies on the Apache HTTP server (The Apache Software Foundation, 2013). The module `mod_wsgi` of Apache allows to host any Python application thanks to the Python WSGI interface. The database structure is based on PostgreSQL with the PostGIS spatial extension. The client side of the application is completely written in Javascript and takes advantage of the ExtJS (<https://www.sencha.com/products/extjs>) library, the `dygraph` library (<http://dygraphs.com>) and CodeMirror 2 (<http://codemirror.net>).

The istSOS has a nested architecture (Figure 11). The kernel of the system is the *istsoslib* which enables the implementation of the SOS standard. Then, the *walib* offers the classes and functions required by the *wainterface* which is the last component of the system and consists in a user-friendly interface.

Figure 11 - istSOS software architecture.

To offer a good quality of service (QoS), in agreement with the INSPIRE directive 2007/2/EC – regulation (EC) No 976/2009 – the system should provide good service performance, capacity and availability. This is translated in practice in the capacity to serve data within defined time limits and number of concurrent users by guaranteeing an elevated up-time.

While istSOS has demonstrated to have good performances its ability of supporting big data is not guaranteed. To this end, in view of having a system capable to support large number of concurrent users and massive datasets while maintaining good performances, a lighting fast cascading proxy server for multiple instances of istSOS have been designed. This solution will bring big-data support with the abilities to horizontally scale over sharded databases of time series. It basically consists in a layer capable to redirect SOS requests and collect the responses to and from different istSOS instances in the cloud. The solution offers a unique access point to retrieve observations and metadata of different WSN (Figure 12). In addition, thanks to this layer it will be possible to handle several concurrent users by using non-blocking network I/O (solving tasks asynchronously) to scale many open connections. As a requirement, the mandatory SOS requests will be supported.

Figure 12 - The proxy solution to horizontally scale istSOS.

Another improvement needed to support a large number of network nodes characterized by minimal resources of their microcontroller is the capacity of having light and high performance method to register observations. Usually, a SOS compliant system uses the *insertObservation* request for the insertion of sensor data. However, this request is characterized by sending a verbose and large XML data structure which does not fit the microprocessor limited RAM and which requires complex and time-consuming elaborations. To overcome the issue a lighter transmission protocol is envisioned. As istSOS already implement a RESTful API, we have plan to implement within this API a new method that will insert new observations provided with a formatted text string (similarly to the UK Met Office FM-12 protocol). The format is defined by parameters values specifically ordered and separated by special characters. In this way, the size of the payload should fit the small memory resources of the microcontroller allowing also to save energy at the node level due to shorter open sessions. This method will act directly at database level to populate it with the observations that come from the sensor network.

With the proposed enhancements istSOS will offer the solution to collect, manage and distribute data. In addition, the service layer should also offer advanced capabilities to:

- aggregate data according to hydrological time intervals
- validate data with different quality control indexes

- elaborate data analysis to produce outputs for end-users

This can be achieved by using the Observation Analysis Tool (OAT) (Cannata et al., 2016) python library, that has been recently developed within the H2020 FREEWAT project (www.freewat.eu). The library offers convenient methods to create time-series object from different data sources (including istSOS), apply processing algorithms, and export results in a number of different format (including istSOS). The library, which is easily extensible, offer the opportunity to implement a number of processes that permit complex data validation and analysis and to save the outputs to an open data repository. Due to its large diffusion and the availability of python action API, the CKAN software has been selected as interface to enhance access to data, metadata and reports. CKAN (Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network; <http://ckan.org/>) is a software solution for open data management and dissemination. CKAN provides modules for spatial indexing, data preview, and service interfaces such as the OpenGIS Catalogue Service (CSW; OGC, 2007). It allows users to find collections of scientific data quickly and easily.

Figure 13 - Workflow of process from standard data into open information

2.4 Communication Layer

Layer description

This layer is responsible to guarantee the data flow among all the EWS components: from the hardware layer (sensor nodes) to the end users (user interfaces). We can individuate three classes of communication (see Figure 14) depending on the nature of the involved device types:

- **Device to Device (D2D)** – where devices communicate with each other
- **Device to Server (D2S)** – where data collected by a device is sent to a server
- **Server to Server (S2S)** – where data in a server is shared amongst other servers for analysis.

Figure 14 - Three types of connections for the communication layer.

While the communication S2S is in general exploited by means of wired Internet connections (Ethernet) and is nowadays available in all the server centres and do not require any particular design, the D2D and D2S types should be carefully evaluated.

The communication layer can be decomposed in four main substructures:

- the transmission medium;
- the communication protocol;
- the messaging technology;
- the transmission strategy.

Transmission medium is a pathway that carries the information from a sender to a receiver. Data are transmitted by using different types of cables or waves, normally through electrical or electromagnetic signals. These signals can be transmitted through copper wires, optical fibres, atmosphere, water and vacuum. Each of these medium have different properties like bandwidth, delay, cost and ease of installation and maintenance. Transmission media is broadly classified into two groups:

- **Wired or guided media:** media are the cables such as twisted pair cable, co-axial cable and fibre optical cable. Each of them has their own characteristics such as transmission speed, effect of noise, physical appearance, cost etc.
- **Wireless or unguided media:** the ways of transmitting data without using any cables. This type of transmission is called Wireless communication. This

transmission uses Microwave, Radio wave, Infrared and other kind of unbound transmission media.

Figure 15 - The communication media schema.

The choice of the transmission medium, and consequently the data transmission capabilities, depends on the following factors (Ali, 2017):

- Bandwidth. It refers to the data carrying capacity of a channel or medium. Higher bandwidth communication channels support higher data rates;
- Radiation. It refers to the leakage of signal from the medium due to undesirable electrical characteristics of the medium;
- Noise Absorption. It refers to the susceptibility of the media to external electrical noise that can cause distortion of data signal;
- Attenuation. It refers to loss of energy as signal propagates outwards. The amount of energy lost depends on frequency. Radiations and physical characteristics of media contribute to attenuation.

In EMS most of the time, due to the remote location of the nodes and the environmental constraints found in the field, the sensors communicate using a wireless technology. Despite to the fact that the infrared (IR) communication is low-power-consumption and due to the difficulty in fulfilling the inter-visibility constraint between the communicating devices, the Radio Frequency (RF) is the most widely adopted solution.

Communication protocol defines the communication range (maximum distance between the devices) and the communication data rate (velocity of transmission). As illustrate in Figure 16, three different classes are individuated in literature (Wong, 2010):

- Home Area Network (HAN), a type of network that facilitates communication among devices within the close vicinity of a home;

- Neighbourhood Area Network (NAN) is a logical communication network built on top of existing physical network infrastructures that focuses on communication among wireless devices in close proximity;
- Wide Area Network (WAN) is a network that extends over a large geographical distance.

Figure 16 - The three type of network based on the coverage area.

The choice of a specific communication protocol depends on the evaluation of desired range area network, energy consumption and data bandwidth (Kuzlu et al., 2014). In Table 9 the most diffused protocols are listed.

Table 9 - Comparison of wireless communication standards, after Mahmood et al. (2015)

	WiMax	GSM	GPRS	UMTS	LTE	ZigBee	Wi-Fi	Bluetooth
Data rate	72 Mbps	14 kbps	171 kbps	> 2Mbps	> 300 Mbps	250 kbps	300 Mbps	1 Mbps
Range	9 Km	10 Km	10 Km	10 Km	10 Km	75 m	100 m	10 m

HAN applications can easily use a widely group of technologies like ZigBee, WiFi, Bluetooth, and Ethernet. ZigBee mesh networks, WiFi mesh networks, as well as long distance wired and wireless technologies, such as WiMAX, GSM, GPRS, 3G and 4G, Digital Subscriber Line (DSL) and Coaxial Cable can implement NAN applications. In WAN, optical communication, GSM, GPRS, 3G and 4G and WiMAX are commonly used as a communication standard between transmission/distribution substations and a utility control centre.

Figure 17 - Wireless communication standards.

The network topology, which is the geographical arrangement of the nodes in an area, determines the physical distances of the devices and therefore the required communication network type (HAN, NAN or WAN). It also ultimately regulates the energy consumption and the transmission strategy. Sharma et al. (2013) recognizes eight basic topologies: point-to-point, bus, tree, star, ring, mesh, circular and grid. Data transmission between nodes takes advantage of sophisticated data routing algorithms aimed at optimizing consumptions, reliability and scalability. As shown in the traditional weather stations networks illustrated in section 2.3 (MeteoSwiss and UK MetOffice) due to the large distance between the nodes, each station is autonomous and is connected to the Internet: directly or through a gateway.

Messaging technologies defines how the communication will be structured. It can be thought of as a language that is used by two or more machines to talk to each other. In practice, it is a set of rules that two devices follow in order to make sense out of the messages that they exchange. This technology is extremely essential in distributed systems where different parts of the same process are carried out at more than one location significantly apart. There are many different messaging technologies that in Al-Fuqaha et al. (2015) are well listed and explained, however, only a small subset is emerging as the most important to power the Internet of things (IoT). Foster (2015) individuated the following:

- HTTP(S): it is a common existing standard, which can be used to deliver XML or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) in the payload;
- The Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP): it was designed by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) for use with low-power and constrained networks. CoAP is a RESTful protocol. It is semantically aligned with HTTP and has a one-to-one mapping to and from HTTP;

- MQ Telemetry Transport (MQTT): it is an open source protocol for constrained devices and low-bandwidth, high-latency networks. It is a publish/subscribe messaging transport that is extremely lightweight and ideal for connecting small devices to constrained networks;
- Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP): it is an open technology for real-time communication, which powers a wide range of applications including instant messaging, presence, multi-party chat, voice and video calls, collaboration, lightweight middleware, content syndication, and generalized routing of XML data.

All the above presented messaging technologies can be used to connect devices (e.g., sensors, mobile devices, single board computers, micro controllers, desktop computers, local servers, servers in a Data Center) in a distributed network (LAN or WAN) via a range of wired and wireless communication technologies including: Ethernet, Wi-Fi, RFID, NFC, Zigbee, Bluetooth, GSM, GPRS, GPS, 3G and 4G.

As depicted in Figure 18, the selectable options of wireless technology and messaging technology depend on the scope of communication:

- message exchanges between device nodes on a Local Area Network (LAN)
- message exchanges between a device node and an Internet based Data Center or between devices via the Internet
- message exchanges between Internet based Data Centers
- messages are exchanges between processes within the same device node

As a result, the choice of the most appropriate messaging solution should be based on the understanding of the architecture and the message/data sharing requirements of the specific target system.

Figure 18 - Connectivity Problem Space

The **transmission strategy** defines how to manage the connections and transmissions within the system. In general, is defined by a series of rules and scheduled tasks that are managed by appropriate algorithms which are composed by three phases:

- data logging: storage of measured data using different schemes to guarantee the access in time to observation and the understanding of transmitted and/or staged data.
- hardware activation: check of the hardware status and wake-up from the sleep mode for the communication period;
- data transmission: establishment of a connection with the end-point, usage of the selected messaging technology to initialize a session and sending of the data;

In the next section, as a result of a literature review, some examples of possible adopted choices for the communication layer are shown.

State of the art

In a monitoring systems, the communication layer is a very important and delicate part because it is responsible of the correct delivery of the information. In the literature and on the market, different solutions for the communication layer have been found. Those considered relevant has been reported herein after.

Libelium WSN is a solution developed by Libelium: a spin-off of the Saragoza University. It offers general WSN components, such as nodes, gateway and software, for the network

management. The Libelium system has been used in some research projects, but it is mostly used to deploy private systems in the context of smart agriculture and smart cities. It is composed by two main technologies: Waspote and a Meshlium. Waspote is a sensor device equipped with different protocols (ZigBee, Bluetooth, GPRS) and frequencies (2.4GHz, 868MHz, 900MHz). It is capable of getting links up to 12km. This device has three kind of power consumption profiles: sleep, deep sleep and hibernate mode. The hibernate mode ensures a consumption of 0.7uA which allows to save battery when it is not transmitting. Meshlium is a Linux router which works as the Gateway of the Waspote Sensor Networks. It can contain 5 different radio interfaces: Wifi 2.4GHz, Wifi 5GHz, 3G/GPRS, Bluetooth and ZigBee. It can integrate a GPS module for mobile and vehicular applications and be solar and/or battery powered. As illustrated in Figure 19, in a standard configuration, Meshlium receives the data from the Waspotes using the ZigBee radio and then forward them to a central server unit using the GPRS and/or store them within its internal memory storage.

Figure 19 - The functionalities of a Libelium system.

Evangelatos et al. (2013), describes the Syndesi framework designed for unifying heterogeneous devices and services in the WSN domain. This is achieved by applying the Representational State Transfer (REST-style) paradigm in combination with the Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) messaging technology to connect networks of sensors, nodes and actuators. Thanks to its lightness it can be used with different communication technologies such as Near Field Communication (NFC), Bluetooth, ZigBee, and 6LoWPAN along with an electrical interface. The RESTful network service deployed in a gateway orchestrates the interaction between the users and the sensor nodes. In the presented example, the users that consisted in Waspotes by Libelium communicate with the gateway using the CoAP, while personal communication devices (smartphone, PC, tablet) used the HTTP protocol. The gateway communicated with the network nodes by means of CoAP.

Gutiérrez et al., 2014, presented an automated irrigation system for optimizing water use in agriculture. The system has a distributed wireless network of soil-moisture and temperature sensors placed in the root zone of the plants. It was tested in a sage crop field for 136 days and water savings of up to 90% compared with traditional irrigation practices of the agricultural zone were achieved. The irrigation system design (Figure 20)

consists of Wireless Sensor Units (WSUs) that using the ZigBee technology transmits soil moisture and temperature data to a Wireless Information Unit (WIU). The WIU uses a GPRS module to transmit the data to a Web server via the public mobile network. The WSU and the WIU are equipped with algorithms to collect and check data. The WSU provide observations that contains identifier, date, time and value to be transmitted via XBee radio modem using a RS-232 protocol. In order to save energy, when not sending data, the microcontroller is set in sleep mode for certain period according to the sensor sampling rate desired, whereas the internal RTCC is running. Once the data are received from WSU components the WIU establishes a connection with the central server unit. If the connection is poor or the communication failed data are stored locally and the process will be triggered hourly, otherwise data are uploaded. To correctly set the date and time within the network, dedicated algorithms performs synchronization tasks. The WSU communicates and retrieves the current date and time from the WIU: this operation is performed at its initialization for the set-up and periodically to eliminate possible drift. The WIU periodically download the correct date and time from the server.

Figure 20 - The irrigation system configuration (Gutiérrez et al., 2014)

Saini et al., 2016 have proposed, developed and tested a hardware module based on Arduino Uno Board and Zigbee wireless technology. The information is received by a specially designed application interface running on a PC connected through Zigbee wireless link. The distance between sensors and PC based system is less than 1 kilometre.

Jolly et al. 2013 presents SNOWWEB, a Wireless Sensor Network equipped with environmental sensors designed to capture distributed meteorological measurements in Antarctica and report them in real-time to a base station. XBee Pro S2B transceivers utilising the ZigBee standard are used combined with high gain omnidirectional antennae to establish reliable multi-hop links with inter-node distances spanning up to 10 km. A ZigBee coordinator is responsible for starting a network and determining its major

configuration parameters, e.g. the operating frequency. A ZigBee router is capable of connecting to other ZigBee routers (and the coordinator) so that either a tree or mesh network is constructed. Finally, a ZigBee device associates itself with a close by ZigBee router or coordinator and transmits all its data to it.

The PermaSense measurement system investigates permafrost with a WSN in the Swiss Alps (Talzi et al., 2007). They used the TinyNode hardware from Shockfish (Dubois-Ferrière et al, 2006, Jeong et al., 2003) which was specifically designed for low-power operation and long distance range radio communications. When placed at soil level, they assessed reliable connectivity of up to 300 meters. It can be extended with a GPRS board that runs Java for controlling the direct access to the Internet. Between sensors nodes, TinyOS messages of up to 42 bytes are exchanged using the the Semtech XE1205 RF chip. The sensor node having a GPRS extension will forward data, also formatted as TinyOS messages, to the TC65 GPRS module from Siemens which contains the Java card. The Java card establishes TCP connections to the data sink server, where data is dumped into database and log files.

Influencing factors and requirements

The communication layer is influenced by:

- Energy consumption
- Transmission media
- Signal coverage
- Node deployment
- Data reporting method
- Data fault tolerance
- Data aggregation
- Security

The communication layer is known to be the main source of power consumption in WSN, thus in batteries only configurations, higher is the transmission rate and shorter is the sensor node lifetime. The challenge here is to find a good balance between node deployment, energy consumption and transmission medium without losing quality and security in the data transmission. Another important parameter is the signal coverage, which should insure to have nodes completely deployed into the covered.

Design

The choices and design of the four main substructures that compose this layer (transmission medium; communication protocol; messaging technology; transmission strategy) are described in this section.

To increase the portability of the system and the simplicity of its installation we have selected the wireless **transmission medium** to connect the sensor nodes with the service layer.

Within the wireless solution we have selected two alternative options as **communication protocol**: the WiFi and the GPRS connection. These alternatives permit to guarantee communication when devices are respectively close or far away from a gateway. They cover the NAN and the WAN solutions. The WiFi option should be used when the node is sufficiently close to an access point used to forward the transmitted data to a central unit; in all the other situations the GPRS module can be integrated in the station to provide direct web access through a mobile internet provider. This choice takes into account the project hypothesis, sustained by marketing and economical studies (GSMA, 2014), that also in developing countries in the forthcoming years the already widely available mobile internet network will be completely cover also the most remote regions.

While the communication layer delivers the data through the use of the described communication protocols, the messaging technology provides a common language between the device and the server.

The selected **messaging technology** is the RESTful style architecture over HTTP/HTTPS that guarantee a request/response pattern. This feature is very important to enable a smart management of D2S data transmission success/failure. The POST method is used to access the transactional functions of SOS (sensor registration and data insertion), but the payload of the XML SOS insertObservation message is heavy. For this reason, considering the hardware constraints, the selected payload is a formatted text string that minimizes the use of the data bandwidth and request execution time, factors that also permit to save energy. In Figure 21 the requested format composed by an header an a payload is shown.

```
POST $uri HTTP/1.1
Host: $server
Accept: */*
Content-Length: $data.length()
Content-Type: text/plain;charset=utf-8
Connection: keep-alive

$payload
```

Figure 21 - HTTP POST request format.

The **transmission strategy**, as previously described, has three main phases: data logging, hardware activation and data transmission. These phases are implemented in algorithms written in C++ and deployed on the Arduino board to be used by the node general logic.

The software is structured with standard interfaces that enable the easy interchange of different devices like ESP8266 or SIM800.

The communication process that handles the three phases is represented in the Figure 22. During the initialization it verifies and sets the Hardware Communication Module (HCM). Then, the process verifies if there's any data not yet transmitted (staging in a temporary log) and if it time for transmitting data to the server. If the two conditions are met, after a data aggregation configured depending on the variable type, the data transmission process is activated. If any error occurs the procedure re-iterates the transmission for a defined number of times. In case of continue failure, data remains in the staging log and are considered in the next transmission.

Figure 22 - Main communication layer algorithm.

The algorithm for initializing the communication hardware is illustrated in Figure 23. It starts with checking if the communication hardware module is installed and, if this is the case, a reset procedure is executed to erase any possible existing incorrect configuration. The next steps are to set the access point configuration parameters and to verify if connection can be correctly established. If one of the previous step fails, coded error messages are raised and logged, so that easy debugging is possible.

Figure 23 - Initialize process algorithm.

The data transmission process is illustrated in Figure 24. The process start with the HCM wake-up and end with the shutdown so that when the process is not executed energy is saved. Once the HCM is activated a connection with the access point is started and then, if successful, other connection with the server is initialized (HTTP/HTTPS RESTful connection). If the active sessions do not raise any errors, the core part of this algorithm is executed: data are formatted according to the istSOS fast insert method and sent to the service layer.

Figure 24 - Algorithm for sending data (phase 3) .

The logical diagram of data logging phase is shown in Figure 25. This interface provides a simple functionality which moves data from the 'temp' folder to the 'log' folder. The 'temp'

folder archives all the raw data that are not yet sent to the server. On the contrary, the 'log' folder stores all the successfully sent data as back-up. This capacity, to save data that were successfully sent and staging those that are to be transmitted, permits to automatically synchronize the node with the server, without losing information, even if communication problems happened.

Figure 25 - Algorithm for the logging phase.

3 Deviation from Work Plan (Heading1 style)

With respect to the work plan this deliverable has been redacted with about 15 days delay due to last minute discussion on the sensors to be used, mainly because some sensors were not available on the Sri Lankan market, and its shipping take a considerable amount of time, which is not compatible with a sustainable solution.

4 Conclusions (Heading1 style)

This report regards the system design for the deployment of the 4nse project. The overall system, which enable an EMS, is based on three different layers: the hardware, service and communication layer. Different factors affect the choices taken to ensure the development of a system that fully respects the 4nse mandatory requirements.

The designed EMS will allow to establish a system as described in the next Figure 26. Data collected from the sensor nodes will be stored in a central place to undergo validation procedures and to be shared with other stakeholders. Validated data, tighter with other data sources will then be used to perform processing and analyses that will converge to an interface to support decision making.

Figure 26 - Workflow of the designed Environmental Monitoring System

The design of the system specific components has been described in details in this documents. The four main open technologies that this design relies on are:

- Arduino
- SOS
- istSOS
- CKAN

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